

WEIGHTING OF INDIAN SILK.

BY C. R. N. REDDY AND B. S. SRIKANTAN.

Weber (*Textilber.*, 1936, 17, 147) has made a detailed study of the tin weighting process on silk fibres and considers that stannic phosphate formed as a result of the action of the unhydrolysed stannic chloride and the di-sodium phosphate of the fixing bath has got a detrimental effect on the fibres. Attempts have been made to substitute tin with other heavy metals like zinc (Berg and Imhoff, U.S.P., 1926, 1579628) and lead (Berg, Imhoff and Heiberg, U.S.P., 1935, 1990449, and 1990450). But in these patents a treatment with tin as a preliminary to the process is considered necessary. However, a more recent patent (Rotheli, U.S.P., 1935, 2010324), in weighting with lead under certain experimental conditions covered by the patent, completely avoids the use of tin. It is claimed that a weighting of 200% is obtained without adversely affecting the tensile strength of the fibres,

In India silks are not generally weighted before selling but the bulk of them are sold in a raw state (private communication from the sericultural expert, Madras). The following paper describes the results of a detailed study of the conditions of the weighting of Indian silk with lead acetate directly. Two varieties of silk locally known as *Eri*-silk and the Mysore-Japanese cross were chosen for the study.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Weighting Procedure.—Exactly weighted quantities of silk (usually 0.5 g.) were kept immersed in 50 c.c. of the weighting solution for a definite time. Then the fibres were thoroughly washed with large amounts of water and were dried at 78° in an air oven for one hour. The increase in weight noted and the percentage weighting calculated. The fibres before weighting were also kept in the drying chamber and it was assumed that the humidity of atmosphere did not vary appreciably during the days the experiments were conducted. The density of the weighting solution was noted by means of Westphal balance.

Breaking Strength.—Instead of measuring the tensile strength as such, the weight necessary to break a definite length of the fibre under free suspension was noted. Six inches of fibre were suspended by corks

held in a clamp. Weights were added to a small pan at the other end till the fibre snapped. The weight of the pan together with that of the added weight was taken as the breaking strength of the fibre. For each sample a number of readings were taken and the average value of the breaking strength was recorded. For the untreated *Eri*-silk it was 95 g. and for untreated *Mysore-Japanese cross* it was 100 g. The individual readings did not vary more than 2%.

The Optimum Hydrogen-ion Concentration of the Weighting Bath.— Different strengths of lead acetate solutions were brought to various p_H values by the addition of 25% ammonium hydroxide. The p_H was determined colorimetrically with cresol-red as the indicator. The following table gives the relation between the p_H values of the weighting solution, the increase in weight and the tensile strength of the treated fibres.

TABLE I.

Mysore-Japanese cross silk.

Time of weighting = 1 hr. Temp. = 28.5°.

	A. Strength of soln. = 1.75.						B. Strength of soln. = 1.31.						
p_H	...	7.4	7.6	8.0	8.4	8.8	9.5	7.4	7.6	8.0	8.4	8.8	9.5
% Increase in wt.	...	0.4	4.82	7.0	8.62	9.3	10.0	1.51	3.9	7.2	8.0	8.2	9.5
Breaking strength (g.)	...	100	98	100	100	96	95	96	102	114	110	100	98
Appearance	...	[...]	[...]	Fair	[...]	[...]	Dull.	[...]	[...]	Fair	[...]	[...]	Dull.

It is seen from the above table that considering the quality of the silk after weighting in relation to its breaking strength and appearance, a p_H value between 8.4 yields the best results. In the following experiments a p_H value of 8.0 has been used throughout.

Time of Weighting.— Table II shows that weighting mostly occurs in the first half an hour and further appreciable increase is not indicated by prolonged treatment. On the contrary a further treatment has a detrimental action on the quality of the silk. In the case of the *Eri*-silk the appearance is rendered dull.

TABLE II

Temp. 28.5. $p_H = 8.0$.

Time (min) ...	Silk : Mys.-Jap. cross.				Silk : Mys.-Jap. cross.				Silk : Eri.		
	A. Strength of soln. = 1.56.				B. Strength of soln. = 1.05.				C. Strength of soln. = 1.05.		
	15	30	60	120	15	30	60	120	30	60	120
% Increase in wt. (g.)	3.9	7.1	7.3	8.2	—	4.5	4.5	5.8	4.5	6.4	6.5
Breaking strength (g.)	97	125	100	96	95	100	100	96	94	92	96
Appearance ...	[... Fair...] Dull.				[... Fair ...] Dull.				Dull Dull Dark.		

Influence of the Concentration of the Weighting Bath.—Experiments were next performed to find the optimum concentration that would be necessary for the maximum absorption of the salt. Solutions of different strengths ($p_H 8.0$) were kept in crystallising basins and weighed quantities of silk were immersed in each of them for 30 minutes at a temperature of 28.5°. The data are presented in Fig. 1 for Eri-silk and Mys.-Jap. cross. In general it is noted that the Eri-silk has a higher weighting capacity than the Mys.-Jap. cross. But it acquires a deep yellow colour as soon as it is brought into contact with the lead acetate solution. The silk loses its

gloss. The deep yellow colour is persistent even after the repeated washings but becomes lighter on a further treatment with sodium hydrogen phosphate or silicate. The weighting, in both cases, at first increases with the strength of the bath and soon reaches a saturation value at sp. gr. 1.25, after which it is steady.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to Eri-silk and Mys.-Jap. silk.

Influence of Temperature.—Tables III and IV shows the influence of temperature of the bath on weighting. It is evident that a variation of temperature from 20° and 40° does not appreciably affect the weighting, but it produces a considerable deterioration in the quality of the silk as seen from its appearance and its tensile strength.

TABLE III.

Temp.	Conc. (sp. gr.)	<i>Eri-silk.</i>		
		% Increase in wt.	Breaking strength.	Remark
20°	1'05	4'24 g.	98 g.	Dull
	1'53	10'22	99	"
	1'91	10'14	92	Very dull.
28'5°	1'05	4'5	94	Pale yellow.
	1'53	10'6	95	Dull.
	1'91	10'4	96	Very dull.
40°	1'05	3'95	95	Deep yellow
	1'50	10'34	98	" "
	1'91	10'40	94	Dull yellow.

TABLE IV.

<i>Jap.-Mys. cross silk.</i>				
20°	1'05	4'4	98	Dull.
	1'56	7'4	92	"
	1'93	8'1	100	Very dull.
28'5°	1'05	4'5	95	Fair.
	1'56	7'1	125	"
	1'93	7'4	102	Not fair.
40°	1'05	2'1	112	Fair.
	1'56	7'2	100	"
	1'93	8'6	102	Dull.
50°	1'56	7'6	98	Very dull.

For this silk, a temperature of about 28'5° and a concentration of 1'56 (sp. gr.) seem to be the best conditions.

Maximum Weighting Capacity.—It is claimed by the patents referred to in this paper that a weighting as high as 200% could be obtained without any adverse effect on the strength of the fibres. Table V gives the maximum weighting capacity of Mysore-Japanese cross silk under the

conditions described. The silk was first treated with lead acetate solution, washed well with water and then kept for 5 minutes in a fixing bath of 5° Be., of sodium hydrogen phosphate, washed well and dried. This process was repeated till it had an adverse effect on the fibres. A weighting of 105% is obtained.

TABLE V.

Sp. gr. of weighting bath = 1.32. Temp. = 28°. p_{H} = 8.0.

No. of treatment	...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
% Increase in weight	...	7.4	10.0	21.2	45.06	68.24	90.43	104.86
Breaking strength (g.)	...	120	110	105	105	105	105	105

S U M M A R Y.

1. An attempt has been made to weight two varieties of Indian silk (*Eri* and *Jap.-Mys.* cross) directly with lead acetate.

2. The optimum hydrogen-ion concentration of the weighting bath has been found to be 8.0.

3. The weighting is mostly a quick process taking place in first few minutes but the fibres can be loaded however to an extent of 105% increase in weight by alternate weighting and fixing treatment.

4. The weighting increases till the solution has sp. gr. 1.25 after which a further increase in the strength of the solution does not affect it.

5. Variation in temperature from 20°-40° does not increase the weighting but has a bad effect on the fibres as seen from appearance and tensile strength. An optimum temperature of 28.5° is recommended.

6. In general Mysore-Japanese cross is more suitable for weighting treatment than the *Eri*-silk, since the latter acquires an undesirable deep colour and loses its tensile strength, though it is capable of getting itself weighted more than the former in the treatment.

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CHEMICAL ENGINEERING LABORATORY,
ANDHRA UNIVERSITY, WALTAIR AND
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE, KUMBAKONAM.

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